

of deadhearts and silver shoots.

The data on pests and grain yield for each planting were plotted (see figure). These conclusions were drawn:

1. Stem borer occurrence was below the economic threshold (5%) on crops planted in September and from December to June.

2. Gall midge incidence was low on crops planted from September to January and in May and June.
3. The normal times of planting in the three seasons — September in samba, January in navarai, and June in sornavari — are ideal. Crops yielded higher than average,

12.5 kg/40 m² (3.1 t/ha). Among the three seasons the highest yield was recorded in navarai.

4. In a season, early or late plantings should be accompanied by timely plant protection measures to avoid yield losses to stem borers and gall midges. ■

Minimum insecticide for rice pest control

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Monitoring pest populations on rice and adopting economic thresholds have minimized insecticide spraying in the village of Buddam, Andhra Pradesh.

The average number of sprays before starting an ICORP project was 2.1 sprays in the wet season and 2.7 sprays in the dry season. But when sprays were made only when needed, the average number was reduced to as low as zero sprays in the 1977-78 wet season. Spraying was done only once on 9.72 ha and in the remaining 395 ha a good crop was raised without spraying at all. In general, economic loss due to insect pests was avoided during the period of the project (Table 1). And fewer sprays were made without loss in yield.

Field sample plots provide data to initiate control operations. Plots 0.4 ha in size and representative of varieties and dates of planting are selected, and 5 m² in each provides the area for counting deadhearts at 15, 30, 55 days after transplanting (DT) and silver shoots at

15 and 35 DT. Counts on 50 hills at random provide the data for other pests.

When the pest density or damage is above an economic threshold (Table 2) in a large number of sample plots, a general survey of farmers' fields is undertaken. Insecticide is applied in fields where an economic threshold has been exceeded.

Other benefits also have been noticed. Incidence of pests in general was low, and the onset of incidence was delayed compared to surrounding areas. Predators of brown planthopper and parasites of gall midge and stem borer contributed increasingly to natural control.

In implementing integrated control, economic thresholds were modified in three cases:

1. In the dry season, stem borer attack develops within 15-20 DT. As the crop at this stage has very few tillers, stem borer attack can result in seedling death and gaps in the field. It is desirable to spray insecticide when the damage reaches 5% deadhearts. Deadheart counts must be taken 15, 30, and 55 DT.
2. Brown planthopper large-scale egg laying occurs during favorable climatic conditions in the preflowering and postflowering stages. Nymph density instead of adult

Table 2. Tentative economic thresholds for pest control. Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, Bapatla, India.

Pest	Threshold
Stem borers	10% deadhearts
Gall midge	5% silvershoots
Green leafhopper) Brown leafhopper)	25 insects/hill
Leaffolder	3 damaged leaves/hill
Cutworms) Rice hispa) Grasshoppers)	1 insect/hill

density provides a better basis for control operations. The presence of 25 nymphs/hill was found to be a useful economic threshold.

3. Since it is difficult to locate the climbing cutworm caterpillars, a better indicator than density is cut panicles. The presence of 5 cut panicles/m² should be the threshold for insecticidal spraying. ■

Effect of volume of insecticide spray on brown planthopper mortality

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Reducing the volume of water in insecticide spray minimizes the cost of farm labor to carry water to the area of application. To determine whether insecticide toxicity is affected by spray volumes, 250, 500, and 1,000 liters insecticide solutions/ha were sprayed on 30- to 35-day-old TN1 potted plants at a rate of 0.75 kg ai/ha using an atomizer run by an air compressor. Beginning one day after treatment (DAT) 20 female adult brown planthoppers were caged on treated plants at 5-day intervals. Insect mortality was recorded 48 hours after caging.

Table 1. Effect of insecticide sprays on rice yield in Bapatla, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Year	Wet season				Dry season			
	ICORP village		Control village		ICORP village		Control village	
	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)
1974-75 ^a	2.1	4.23	2.8	3.57	2.7	3.15	3.2	3.33
1975-76	1.4	3.75	2.1	2.53	0.7	4.50	3.1	4.40
1976-77	0.3	5.00	0.2	3.33	0.3	4.18	2.3	4.19
1977-78	0.0	4.60 ^b 1.77 ^c	0.2	2.65	1.5	3.52	1.6	3.18
1978-79	0.1	4.01	0.4	3.65	—	—	—	—
1979-80	0.3	4.20	0.5	4.00	—	—	—	—

^aBase year. ^bYield before a cyclone. ^cYield after a cyclone.